

Electrochemical behaviour of some potential biologically active 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides

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Abstract : A series of azomethinesulphonamide derivatives were synthesized by condensation of vanilline with sulphonamides and their redox behaviour was studied at different pH and concentration. The structures of the synthesized compounds were established by spectral (FT-IR, ¹H NMR) and elemental analysis. Polarographic and cyclic voltammetric data for the redox behaviour of the synthesized compounds was suggestive of the reductive cleavage of the -N=C < pharmacophore.

Keywords : Azomethines, polarography, cyclic voltammetry, coulometry.

Introduction

Azomethine compounds find numerous applications in analytical chemistry^{1,2}. Azomethines are well known for their biological applications as antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer and antiviral agents^{3,4}. Schiff bases are used as substrates in the preparation of a large amount of bioactive and industrial compounds⁵⁻⁹.

Some studies have indicated that amines were products of the electrochemical reduction of imines in protic solvents¹⁰⁻¹². Under aqueous condition, the reduction was shown to consist of four-electron, four-proton transfer, which converted the >C=N- linkage to a -CHNH-group¹³. However the hydrolysis of the Schiff bases into the parent carbonyl compound complicated the situation in protic media.

In the present work, electrochemical behaviour of synthesized azomethines was examined at Hg electrode in aqueous medium. All synthesized azomethines exhibit a single irreversible four-electron reduction wave¹⁴.

Experimental

Synthesis of 4-[(E)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-N-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides :

A solution of 4-hydroxy-(3-methoxy)benzaldehyde

(0.01 M; 5 mL ethanol) was taken in a flask and sulphonamide derivative (0.01 M; 5 mL ethanol) was slowly added with continuous stirring. The contents of the flask were refluxed for three hours and left over night in an ice bath. The Schiff base was separated out collected and further purified by recrystallization from ethanol to obtain lime yellow crystals of azomethines (**1a-d**). Melting points of the synthesized compounds were determined in open capillaries. The purity of the compounds was checked using precoated thin layer chromatography (TLC) plates (Merck, 60 F) using chloroform/methanol (8 : 2) solvent system. The synthetic route to the required compounds is outlined in Scheme 1.

Similarly, other derivatives were prepared by using the substituted derivatives of sulphonamides such as pyridine, thiazole and methoxazole. Characteristics of synthesized compounds were given in Table 1. FTIR spectra of all the compounds were recorded by making KBr pellet on FTIR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu IR 21). NMR spectra of azomethines were recorded on Bruker 400 MHz NMR spectrophotometer, IR (KBr) cm⁻¹; 3299 (OH), 905 (S-N str.), 1366 (O=S=O), 3263 (N-H str.), 3018 (C-H str. aro.), 1598 (C=N str.); NMR (methanol) ppm : 6.6-7.3 (Ar-H), 3.9 (Ar-OH), 5.5 (-CH=N-), 3.8 (O-CH₃).

Scheme 1

Table 1. Characteristics of 4-[(E)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-N-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides

Compd.	R	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. formula ^a	Mol. weight
1a	-H	289	56	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S	306
1b		323	61	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S	359
1c		365	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	389
1d		367	66	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₃ S	387

^aAll compounds gave consistent C, H and N analysis.

Electrochemical studies of 4-[(E)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-N-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides :

Polarographic measurements were made on Elico CL 362 differential pulse polarograph consisting of a three electrode assembly. Triple distilled mercury was used in the dropping mercury electrode which was used as the working electrode, saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and platinum wire were used as reference and the auxiliary electrodes respectively. All the solutions, prepared for electrochemical studies were purged for 10 min with pu-

rified nitrogen to remove dissolved oxygen. All pH-metric measurements were made on a Decible DB-1011 digital pH meter fitted with a glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode for reference, which was previously standardized with buffers of known pH.

Procedure :

The differential pulse polarographic studies were carried out using 1.0 mL (5×10^{-3} M) solution of the depolarizer (1a-d), 1.0 mL of 1.0 M KCl and 8.0 mL of appropriate buffer. The influence of various buffers (phosphate, Britton-Robinson and acetate buffers) on the ana-

lytical signals was also studied and it was found that the reduction peaks were well defined in the phosphate buffer. Phosphate buffers were used for maintaining the pH throughout the investigations at various concentrations and at different pulse amplitudes. Experiments were carried out to study the influence of different concentrations of the depolarizer and different pulse amplitudes on the reduction process of the synthesized 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides.

Coulometric studies of 4-[(E)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-N-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides :

Controlled potential coulometry was employed for determining the number of electrons (*n*) transferred in the electrode process. The number of electrons *n*, was calculated from the charge consumed by 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulphonamide. The charge consumed was determined in acidic medium. For this purpose 1 mL of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulphonamide (5×10^{-3} M) solution 100 mL of 1.0 M KCl and 8.0 mL of phosphate buffer were placed in the cell and electrolysis was carried out. During electrolysis, the solutions were continuously stirred and purged with nitrogen gas. The number of electrons (*n*) was calculated using the equation $Q = nFN$, where *Q* is the charge in coulombs, *F* is the Faraday constant and *N* is the number of moles of the substrate.

Cyclic voltammetric studies of 4-[(E)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-N-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides :

Cyclic voltammograms of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides (1×10^{-2} M) were recorded in dimethylformamide in phosphate buffers, at glassy carbon electrode (GCE). All compounds exhibited a four electron, irreversible, diffusion controlled well defined peak in the pH range 2.0 to 11.5. The cathodic peak can be attributed to the reduction of -CH=N-NH- group. In this pH range no anodic peak could be realized indicating towards the irreversible nature of the electrode process.

Results and discussion

Differential pulse polarograms (DPP) were recorded in phosphate buffers in the pH range 2.0 to 11.5. The effect of pH, pulse amplitude and different concentrations of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulphonamide on the reduction peak were studied (Fig. 1). All 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides exhibited one well defined polarographic peak in the pH range of 2.0 to 11.5. Overall four electron reduction process was observed.

The linearity of the plot of i_d vs pulse amplitude indicated towards the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode reaction. Linear increment in the cathodic peak current with concentration further confirmed the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process. Shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards negative potential indicated that the reduction became more difficult which can be attributed to increasing Lewis basicity of the solvent (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Plots of $-E_p$ vs pH of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulphonamides at conc. 5×10^{-3} M.

The reversibility of the process was checked by recording polarograms of different concentrations of the depolarizer (5×10^{-3} to 2.5×10^{-2} M) and it was observed that $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential with rise in concentration of depolarizer. This behaviour clearly indicated the irreversible nature of the electrode process which was further confirmed by the logarithmic analysis i.e. the slope of the plot of $-E_{d.e.}$ vs $[\log (i/i_d - i) - 0.546 \log t]$ was greater than $59.2/n$ mV. The value of heterogeneous rate constant for the electrode process was calculated from the plot of $-E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log [i/i_d - i] - 0.546 \log t^{15-17}$. Electrochemical characteristics of 4-[(*E*)-(4-

Table 2. Electrochemical characteristics of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamides, conc. $5 \times 10^{-3} M$

Compd.	R	$-E_p$ (V)	i_d (μA)	αn_a	I	$\partial E_{1/2}/\partial pH$, V/pH	$D_0^{1/2}$ ($cm^2 s^{-1}$)	$K_0^{f,h}$ ($cm s^{-1}$)
1a	-H	1.63	12.09	0.37	0.73	0.081	3×10^{-2}	4.0×10^{-6}
1b		1.22	9.92	0.20	0.64	0.067	2.6×10^{-2}	1.86×10^{-4}
1c		1.64	10.60	0.28	0.60	0.072	2.5×10^{-2}	2.5×10^{-5}
1d		1.21	9.33	0.21	0.57	0.070	2.3×10^{-2}	5.6×10^{-4}

hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamides have been compiled in Table 2.

In cyclic voltammetry, the effect of pH on potential and diffusion current of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide was also re-

corded. Effect of scan rate on the reduction of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide was also examined in phosphate buffer at pH 7.0. The scan rate was varied from 50 to 250 $mV s^{-1}$ at a fixed concentration of depolarizer. The plot of i_{pc} vs $v^{1/2}$

Scheme 2

(v = scan rate) was a straight line passing through the origin which indicated the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process. The cathodic peak potential shifted towards more negative potential with increasing scan rate, as expected for irreversible electron transfer^{18,19}.

Redox mechanism :

On the basis of DPP, CV and coulometric studies following mechanism for the reduction of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)-benzenesulphonamides can be postulated (Scheme 2).

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